

'Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD Supervision' Method & Guide for Supervisors

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Abstract

This paper outlines the main features of a PhD supervision approach developed over the last ten years across two universities that draws together multiple features of empirically identified best practices to maximise completions and reduce typical completion times to within 3 years whilst ensuring high quality thesis outcomes. The supervision approach was initially devised for long-thesis PhDs and is especially suited to addressing the difficulties of international students and students from fields such as Design in which the skills learned in undergraduate education are in a different direction to those needed for formal research.

Dr Terence Love developed the Quality 3 year Fast-Track Supervision approach to address five issues:

- Achieving 100% completion rate for PhD candidates
- Achieving completions within government specified deadline
- Supporting completion of PhDs within 3 years
- Achieving similar or higher quality PhD thesis outcomes than by conventional supervision
- Achieving similar outcomes for international students disadvantaged by language and cultural factors, and PhD candidates disadvantaged by lack of research training and reasoning skills in their undergraduate education (e.g. those with Design undergraduate education).

The approach builds on research into best practice in PhD supervision and research training along with practical empirical testing and evaluation of different aspects of the PhD supervision approach over more than a decade and of educational research analyses of the processes of undertaking and supervising PhDs.

A focus of this formally-defined best-practice PhD supervision approach has been on improving Design-related PhDs across a wide variety of design disciplines. The underlying educational basis of the approach would also be expected to apply to PhD supervision across the Design spectrum and wider, and also to research project supervision in Masters by Research and Honours programs.

This new 'Quality 3-year Fast Track PhD supervision' method draws on the extensive research on PhD best practices available worldwide and the ongoing development and testing of specific supervisory methodics by the author across multiple PhD students. The quality 3-year Fast Track supervision method has the following attributes:

- Provides PhD candidates with a full suite of professional doctoral competencies in research methods, research practices, academic writing skills and personal professional doctoral competencies.
- Improves quality of research practice, outputs and findings of Design PhD candidates.
- Maximizes retention and completions
- Ensures PhD thesis completion on time, including examination of PhD and revisions.
- Addresses the weaknesses of conventional research training courses
- Is well suited to international PhD candidates disadvantaged by language, writing and cultural issues, and PhD candidates with an undergraduate education in Design lacking in research training, and critical analytical reasoning skills.
- Ensures new doctors have the competencies necessary to immediately engage in and manage professional activities in research in academia and in industry and commerce.
- New doctors following this program gain the experience and skills to supervise their own PhD students using this Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD supervision approach.

The 'Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD supervision' program is formally defined at a week by week level to provide PhD candidates with layered development of the full suite of doctoral competencies in parallel with undertaking their research and writing their PhD thesis.

Keywords

PhD, supervision, completions, thesis, quality

Introduction

This paper outlines the 'Quality 3-year Fast-track PhD Supervision' method developed and tested by the author for supervision of long-thesis PhDs. This supervision method and its associated 3 year PhD program is particularly suited to PhDs in Design Research Together, they also address the specific disadvantages of international students and provide supportive training in research methods, reasoning and academic writing for those coming to PhD research from undergraduate Design degrees.

In the late 1990s, the author identified that quality of PhD supervision and its processes were potentially the most significant factor in guaranteeing successful and timely PhD outcomes. This position has become increasingly supported by research into PhD supervision quality by a variety of educational researchers (See, for example, Chen, Holbrook, & Absalom, 2001; Delany, n.d.; Sinclair, 2004). This focus on the benefits of better supervision practices contrasts, however, with the popular 'how to get a PhD' literature in which guidance for improving PhD outcomes focuses on the PhD candidate's weaknesses (see, for example, Nyquist, 2001; Phillips & Pugh, 1992).

The 'Quality 3-year Fast-track PhD Supervision' method outlined in this paper was designed, developed and refined to address the following educational design constraints:

- Targets completion of PhDs within 3 years. Full completion time includes everything from acceptance to enroll in the university to examination and award of the PhD. This contrasts with current completion claims which are often counted to 'time of first submission of thesis'

- Aims for majority of PhD candidates full completing their PhD within 3.5 years and 100% within maximum 4 years. Typically, using this supervision process, candidates submit their thesis less than 3 years from the date of admission to university to undertake the PhD program.
- High quality PhD outcomes. Aim is a quality of PhD thesis outcomes better than those resulting from conventional supervision practices with a similar cohorts of PhD candidates
- 100% completions by PhD students viewed as normal.
- Long-thesis PhD (max 100,000 words, typical 75,000 word thesis plus references) written and supervised in English. The assessment of a long-thesis PhD is wholly on the research and analyses of the PhD candidate as expressed in the PhD thesis.
- Resolves all issues with:
 - International PhD candidates disadvantaged by language and cultural issues, and differences in research culture.
 - Local and international PhD candidates with weak academic writing skills.
 - Local and international PhD candidates with weak or non-existent research training and reasoning skills: typical of many candidates with undergraduate Design education backgrounds.

The design and development of the 'Quality 3-year Fast-Track Supervision' method was strongly shaped by several sources. Overall, it is empirically grounded in the author's observation of, and discussions with, dozens of PhD students, with the use of the supervision method on PhD and Masters students the author has supervised and advised, and on observations of aspects of this supervision method used by other PhD supervisors. The initial developments were as a result of a personal investigation into best practices in PhD thesis structuring and the use and development of Dr Charles Perry's model of the five chapter thesis in the late 1990s (Love, 2001, 2005; Perry, 1994, 1998). In the period 2000-2003, the author was involved in supporting PhD education in the School of Management Information Systems and the We-B Research Centre at Edith Cowan University (ECU) whilst involved in research into improving PhD research in Design. Alongside, were influences from others researching into aspects of PhD education and assessment, especially supervision. Of particular note is the work of Prof Allyson Holbrooke and colleagues at Newcastle University (e.g. <http://www.newcastle.edu.au/research/expertise/135050.html>) and other Australian education researchers from that period (see, for example, Bourke, Scevak, & Cantwell, 2001; Sinclair, 2004). Professor Bill Hutchinson and Pro-Vice Chancellor Ron Oliver (Oliver, 2008), both of ECU provided advice and support at various stages. More formally, the research aligned with parallel research into the future of doctoral education undertaken with Professor Brynjulf Tellefsen of BI in Oslo. The section in this paper on changes in doctoral education draws heavily on findings from this latter research (Tellefsen & Love, 2002).

The supervision method outlined below differs strongly from conventional advice to improving supervision which concentrates on the 'responsibilities' of supervisors (see, for example, Monash University, 2000) or simply exhorts universities to provide 'quality supervision' (see, for example, ESRC, 2009) without specifying it in detail. Instead, it provides a highly structured and empirically justified basis for each aspect of supervision right down to a detailed week by week program modified as necessary by the details of the candidates PhD project.

Before outlining the supervision method, this paper first reviews changes and factors that have driven and are driving the need for a radically new view on PhD supervision. The following sections of the paper first review the changing dynamic of PhD education. They then focus on the detail of the design 'problem' of designing better supervision.

PhD Education is Changing

The PhD is a relatively new doctorate that originated in Germany. From there it was adopted within the US and from there spread to the UK and Norway and onwards. There are two main forms of PhD education:

- The preparation of a 'long thesis' assessed by other doctors. This is most dominant in the UK and is based on traditions shaped by the medieval university systems of Bologna, Salerno, Paris and Oxford (Catholic Encyclopedia, 2001a, 2001b). Some early forms of doctoral study contained preliminary examinations, *privata* and *licentia docend* necessary to apply for the *inceptio*, final examination, at which the doctorate was conferred and biretta imposed. These preliminary studies are more evident in the second form of PhD.
- The PhD from Germany adopted in the late 19th century by Yale and other American universities with taught courses preceding a smaller research project and thesis or dissertation than that found in the long-thesis PhD (Reinstein, 1997).

PhD education has been changing in fundamental ways for some time (Deem, 1998). In Western societies such as the European Community, the USA, and Australia, PhD education is increasingly viewed in terms of its role in the fulfillment of national aims and objectives (see, for example, Academy of Finland, 1997; Association of American Universities Committee on Graduate Education, 1998; Canadian Agri-Food Research Council, 1997; Commission of The European Communities, 2000; Council for Science and Technology, 2001; EPSRC, 2001; ESRC, 2001; Gaff, 2001; Kemp, 1999; Leith, 1995; Ministry of Research and Information Technology, 1998; National Endowment for the Arts, 2001; National Endowment for the Humanities, n.d.; National Science Foundation, 1998, 2001a, 2001b; Norwegian Research Council, 1998; The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education, 2001). Reviews of national roles of research and research training have been strongly critical of the effectiveness and efficiency of PhD education (see, for example, Nyquist & Woodford, 2000).

Analysis of the future of doctoral education by Tellefsen and Love (2002) indicated that changes in PhD education are driven by several factors including:

- Applied and practitioner-oriented research is likely to form an increasing proportion of research overall.
- Increasing pressures towards 100% PhD completion rates.
- PhDs to be completed in shorter times.
- Universities behave more like for-profit competitive businesses.
- Pressures on universities to make money from research and PhD education.
- PhDs will have more of a commercial focus and less of an academic focus.
- The diversity of forms of PhD education will increase.
- Universities PhD programs will compete on price, research uniqueness, research

reputation, and commercial outcome

- A lower proportion of PhD dissertations will be published publicly, due to the proprietary needs of collaborating businesses to secure research findings to build competitive advantage.
- The reputations of universities and schools will become more important for all stakeholders.
- There are likely to be more alliances between universities, research centres, government service providers and businesses. These alliances will have little internal rivalry, but keen competition with rival alliances.
- More PhDs will be undertaken in networks and teams.
- There are likely to be an increase in the number and variety of networks across disciplines, research institutions and with businesses.

There is a significant financial aspect, in many developed western countries such as Australia, tertiary education is a significant international business and earner of foreign currency. In Australia, education services are the third largest export earner after coal and iron ore and is valued 2007-2008 at over \$14billion per annum (Access Economics Pty, 2009). Taking an economic focus and applying economic rationalization of higher education puts competitive pressures on PhD awarding institutions and the areas of scholarship within them as overall university funding is increasing tied to research outcomes including numbers of PhDs awarded that complete within a time limit (see, for example, Kemp, 1999b). This in turn places considerable pressure on all stakeholders within PhD awarding bodies to improve PhD educational outcomes as part of institutions' strategies to maximise their position in relation to new financial realities.

A core aspect of PhD education is its role in intentional national knowledge development. Over the last decade or more, worldwide, governments increasingly direct university-based research and post-graduate research training. For example, in 2000, the Commission of the European Union (EU) proposed new guidelines for EU research activities for 2002-2006 requiring joint effort from the EU member state governments, and the research communities to create a European Research Area (Commission of The European Communities, 2000). The plan calls for cooperation between member states to result in complementary research activities that produce knowledge to both guide and strengthen political agendas. Governments are increasingly requiring that their taxpayer funded support for PhD education results in outcomes that align with national objectives such as:

- Training highly skilled knowledge professionals useful to industry and society
- A pool of individuals with competence in research skills applicable to a variety of circumstances
- The timely creation of new knowledge that supports the fulfilment of national socioeconomic objectives
- Significant improvements to the efficiency and effectiveness of PhD education processes
- Beneficial employment outcomes for PhD candidates

These preferred outcomes contrast strongly with prior perspective on the role 'long thesis' PhD education:

- Individuals with content expertise in a single highly focused topic area

- Research assistants (PhD students) providing economically efficient support for large research projects
- Low cost teaching assistants (PhD students)
- Individuals capable of teaching in universities at a tertiary level (PhD graduates)
- Additions to knowledge in areas of interest to academics and PhD students

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The changes in direction to PhD education can be seen in several countries. The following have been chosen because of their use of long thesis PhD programs or programs that include a significant thesis element.

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The UK long thesis PhD

In the UK, classic long-thesis PhD education has until recently been mainly funded via government research councils through grants to each university. The Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) describes research and research training primarily in terms of creating new scientific knowledge and assumes these support national and social, aims and objectives (EPSRC, 2001). At the other end of the spectrum, the Arts and Humanities Research Council, previously the Arts and Humanities Research Board (AHRB), was created to respond to criticism that Arts and Humanities research was neglected (Dearing, n.d.), and not contributing to national objectives. Contributing to national objectives is now a central focus of PhDs funded by AHRC (AHRC, 2009).

Supervision in UK PhD education is typically relatively, ad-hoc, variable and substantially laissez-faire with around 25% of PhD students identifying problems with supervision (Delany, n.d.).

The US mixed mode PhD

In the US, PhD education is intended to serve national and social interests. This requires funding criteria to be congruent with the criteria used by the Executive Office of the President and Congress (Leith, 1995). The content of PhD research in the US is driven by government and private funding bodies (Woodrow Wilson National Fellowship Foundation, 1998). Funding for PhDs is provided through Federal agencies each with their own socio-economic intents and responsibilities (see, for example, National Science Foundation, 2000, Note 51)(National Endowment for the Arts, 2001)(National Endowment for the Humanities, n.d.). The structure of US PhD education and assessment originated in the adoption by Yale (1861) and other universities of the German smaller doctorate, the 'Doctor of Philosophy' (Johns Hopkins University, 2001; Slater, 2001). Typically, US PhDs consist of a research project and thesis undertaken after satisfactory completion of a program of taught courses providing PhD candidate with necessary doctoral skills to undertake their research project and thesis.

Supervision in the US is typically done by a committee of supervisors that provides breadth of content support for each candidate.

Australian long thesis PhDs

PhD education in Australia follows the UK tradition with programs mainly structured around a 'long thesis' PhD undertaken through solitary study, although there is increasing, though small-scale use of other doctoral modalities. The preference for the title of 'PhD' rather than (say) DCA or Deng results in a major aspect of them being shaped around the long thesis format. Australian universities have recently been placed under strong pressure to improve their effectiveness and efficiency, and improve the contribution of PhD education to fulfilling national, social and industry objectives (see, for example, Kemp, 1999a; Kemp, 1999b). In parallel, Australian universities are reviewing the ways that their PhD education programs can be modified to maximise university income under new funding arrangement in which university funding revenue is linked to the numbers of PhD completions achieved in less than 4 years.

Historically, Australian PhD supervision has focused on the use of a single PhD supervisor. Over the last decade, however, there has been widespread adoption of supervision panels consisting of a supervisory panel chair, a main supervisor with at least one co-supervisor and or associate supervisor. This move to supervisory panels, and reductions in staff work allowance for each PhD supervision, results in tension with best practice for PhD supervision involving weekly face to face contact (Group of Eight Ltd, 2010; Sinclair, 2004) because it requires additional time: for collaboration between supervisors to avoid contradictory advice to the candidate.

Norwegian PhDs – both types

Norwegian PhD education has two forms, the typical 'long thesis' PhD, and the US model of PhD. The medieval UK PhD approach, allowing any scholar, regardless of previous degrees, to demand their PhD thesis, to be judged by other doctors is still allowed, but is increasingly replaced with the US/German PhD model in professional disciplines. PhD education is strongly shaped by the Norwegian Research Council, which has identified the need to shorten the completion time and increase the completion percentage of doctorates.

Norwegian PhD supervision is legally defined. Norwegian law provides each PhD candidate the right to be supported by a committee of at least three supervisors of which some may be external to the PhD institution.

The 'Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD Supervision' method outlined in this paper provides a detailed structural plan for PhD supervision, and for PhD study, that works to address the issues shaped by the changes described above in PhD education to give advantage to institutions in improving their PhD outcomes and funding.

The PhD problem context

As outlined above, dissatisfactions with current approaches to PhD education, particularly those based on the 'long thesis', have been evident for more than a decade in across most stakeholder groups: government, funding bodies, academic institutions, students, the community, and commercial and industrial organisations, with the balance of problems differing across these constituencies. To recap, , problems identified relating to outputs, efficiency and effectiveness of PhD programs have been seen in

terms of wasting government distribution of funding from taxpayers; money that was intended for betterment of the country and of citizen's lives. This position has been a strong theme in the EU, UK and Australia however, it is less strongly argued in the US where PhD education is seen more exclusively as a pathway to a position in university teaching, and both universities and research already have a strong commercial dimension. Underlying these discussions are practical concerns about the quality and appropriateness of PhD education, in relation to the fulfilment of governmental socio-economic and technological objectives.

In practical terms, relating to the pedagogical issues, the criticisms are that traditional PhD education outcomes are marked by:

- Low levels of completion
- High levels of time overrun (in magnitude and incidence)
- High levels of variability in output and quality
- Lack of usefulness of research outcomes for commerce, industry, society and other national priorities and objectives
- Poor collaboration between academia and industry
- Poor return on government funding for post-graduate education

For international PhD students studying to achieve a long-thesis PhD in an English speaking country such as Australia, there have been identified additional problem dimensions in improving PhD education (Harman, 2003):

- Lack of adequate research support
- Problems with the quality and effectiveness of supervision
- Help in designing research projects
- Language problems
- Less deferential working arrangement with supervisors
- Less structure in research direction
- Working space
- Financial problems

In this changing PhD education context, the relative simplicity of structure of PhD education means there are limited pathways to intervene to improve PhD outcomes. The process of designing an improved PhD education, however, is essentially the same as for other forms of education except for the level of autonomy expected of the learner. Developing an improved form for PhD education must address:

- Quality assurance – identifying the criteria or performance indicators that define PhD awards. Identifying suitable means of moderation
- Pedagogical issues – choosing or designing those educational processes that support an individual from graduating at Bachelors or Masters level in developing the skills and competencies to the level required to satisfy a PhD award

The reviews of PhD education discussed earlier indicate that the traditional 'long thesis' PhD programs, based on the use of light-touch laissez-faire supervision to guide research undertaken by a single individual under is not highly effective or efficient in the context of the current changing dynamics of factors defining successful PhD outcomes.

Radical changes to improve PhD supervision offers a straightforward opportunity to address all of the above issues (except working space and financial problems) through a variety of different changes to PhD supervision processes. Focusing on improving supervision processes offers a systemic structurally-based advantage to PhD awarding institutions in line with the advice of Deming (1986) on improving quality of outcomes. The 'Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD Supervision' method outlined below in this paper provides a detailed structural plan for supervision, and for PhD study, that addresses all of the above problems in detail to improve quality of PhD theses, completion outcomes, and improve PhD candidates learning outcomes and study experiences.

Outline of Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD supervision

In its origins, the development of the 'Quality-3-year Fast-Track PhD supervision' method focused on what the author had identified as the most significant three dimensions of supervision

- Empirically-based best practice supervision process
- Careful work study of the activities of PhD candidates, supervisors, and administrators; and all other participants and constituencies, and their interest and relationships, in a candidate's PhD process from start to finish. This latter includes learning associated with research skills, language, writing; and the structure and process of the candidate's writing of their thesis.
- Well defined structural model of PhD thesis

A core part of the analyses that led to the Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD supervision method involved straightforward work study analyses of the detail of tasks and timings, interests, responsibilities, systems, processes, administration and management etc. for all involved in an individual candidate progressing from application to a university to undertake a PhD right through to their award of the PhD as a new doctor and their transition into life activities following their PhD. In parallel, was a study of the findings about factors within a PhD that led to candidates leaving their PhD program unfinished and factors that reduced quality of output and learning.

From these analyses, it was clear that there were substantial opportunities to reduce the time taken for a PhD and at the same time remove many of the factors that result in late or none completions and low quality of learning and outputs. The most obvious way of implementing such a strategy was through the supervision process.

The tasks and timings that emerged from the analyses are outlined in the tables below of 3.5 year and 3 year PhD projects.

A 'typical' 3.5-year Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD comprises the following time components:

- Application: 1 month

- Preparation and approval administration of candidacy and ethics: 4 months
- Extended literature review and preparation for data collection: 5 months
- Data collection: 6 months
- Data analysis: 6 months
- Writing thesis: 7 months
- Contingency, personal crises: 2 months
- Prepare and deliver refereed conference paper: 2 months
- Examination of thesis and revisions plus award administration: 6 months
- Holidays (1 month/ year for 3 years): 3 months
- Total 3.5 years (42 months)

For well-organised students with straightforward carefully chosen PhD topics, the overall period can be reduced to the 'typical' 3 year Fast Track PhD, which comprises the following time commitments:

- Application: 1 month
- Preparation and approval administration of candidacy and ethics: 4 months
- Extended literature review and preparation for data collection: 5 months
- Data collection: 4 months
- Data analysis: 5 months
- Writing thesis: 6 months
- Contingency, personal crises: 2 months
- Examination of thesis and revisions plus award administration: 6 months
- Holidays (1 month/ year for 3 years): 3 months
- Total 3 years (36 months)

The main reasons for late completion are primarily due to unproductive time in a PhD process. Typical unproductive time losses are due to:

- Inefficient university administration (including administration-related decisions by supervisors)
- Candidate drifting off track or changing direction for reasons not directly related to the research problem
- The use of serendipitous, random (rather than systematic) literature explorations and reviews
- Inappropriate choice of PhD research project
- Inefficient or faulty data collection and analysis processes
- Weaknesses in the candidate's work habits
- Inefficient thesis structure,
- Poor thesis writing and editing processes
- Undertaking any process of the PhD to a higher standard than needed
- Personal crises of the student

In a large proportion of conventional long-thesis PhDs, the above 'un-productive time' processes typically amounts to 1-2 years and in many cases can amount in total to several years. In a substantial percentage of cases (typically only around 60% of PhD students complete in the Humanities), un-productive time extends to the point that the candidate withdraws from the PhD program.

All of the above problems can be regarded as problems of poor PhD supervision and hence amenable to improved supervision practices. Good supervision practices can address and remove all of the above issues.

The fundamental problem of developing improved supervision practices is that the style of supervision and the competencies needed of PhD supervisors to address the above issues is radically different from conventional light-touch laissez-faire PhD supervision.

To address and remove the above unproductive time requires, as in the advice for best practice PhD supervision' (see, for example, Sinclair, 2004), for PhD supervisors to take a significant 'hands-on' supervisor/mentor role to managing PhD students learning and research activities. This contradicts strongly with the laissez-faire, anything goes, style of supervision practiced by many supervisors.

This 'best practice' supervision approach also requires significantly different competencies. For example, it is necessary for PhD supervisors to have high-level fluency in all university administrative systems relating to PhDs. Commonly, PhD-related decision-making committees meet on a 1-3 month cycle. For time efficiency, it is necessary for the supervisor to guide the student to ensure their candidacy, ethics and thesis submissions are aligned to the timing of the committees that makes candidacy, ethics and thesis examination decisions. Where this does not happen, the misalignment can result in unproductive wasted time of several months for the PhD candidate. As a different set of supervisory competencies, if things administratively do go astray, it is necessary for the supervisor to have the skills to intervene effectively on behalf of the student to ensure the PhD process comes back on the same timeline in ways that reverse any delays. This will at times necessarily involve the supervisor being involved in strong discussions with the university administration.

Research into best practice supervision indicates it is necessary for the supervisor to meet the PhD candidate frequently: usually weekly at least. These meetings have three roles:

- Keep the candidate's PhD on track
- Develop the PhD candidate's professional skills and competences as a researcher and research manager.
- Pastoral care, including guiding PhD candidates in the personal skills of being a research professional

On the latter issue, from observation, PhD candidates' personal and family issues (and this includes the candidate's own research skill development) are major drivers of delays in PhD completion and non-completion. These include diversion from the research because the research problem is not aligned with the candidate's interest, health and stress issues; family-related health and stress issues (particularly for PhD candidates with young children); random changes in direction to avoid a research issue that a candidate does not have the skills to overcome. Addressing these issues appears to be one of the most central aspects of good supervision pedagogy. To do this, supervisors require personal competencies

that enable them to provide front-line pastoral and personal development mentoring for PhD candidates. They also require the knowledge as to other professional services and approaches that are available to facilitate PhD candidates addressing personal issues that impact on the process of undertaking their PhD, and the formation of their research competences.

In content knowledge and expertise in the area of the candidate's PhD research, it would reasonably be expected that the supervisor be well ahead of the PhD candidate in both knowledge and expertise. PhD projects are for research training of new doctors. Supervisors are experienced, highly competent research professionals. It is reasonable to expect a PhD supervisor to be able to undertake the same research project as the PhD candidate in a shorter time and to a higher standard. From experience, it is easily possible for competent PhD supervisors to be able to stay ahead of the PhD candidate in their review of literature, data collection and analysis and discussion of conclusions. The idea propagated some years ago, that PhD students should, at the conclusion of their PhD, be ahead of their supervisor does not reflect well on the competence and contribution of supervisors. This factor may contribute to explaining the last several decades of poor PhD outcomes in the rates of non-completions and late completions.

A major factor in delay of completion and lack of completions of PhDs comprises PhD candidates having difficulties in writing their PhD theses. At earlier stages in a candidate's PhD, similar problem also occur in delays in writing the candidacy applications, ethics submissions, questionnaires and surveys and literature reviews. These problems have six causes: lack of skill in English as a language (true for both English native speakers and International PhD candidates); lack of skills in reasoning, logic and avoiding fallacies (this is particularly a problem for design students who are heavily trained in the use of rhetoric rather than reasoning and in creating fallacies, rather than identifying and removing them in their writing); lack of skills of academic research-related writing at a doctoral level; lack of skills at identifying and bounding the scope of a project; absence of skills of structuring and managing very large documents, particularly those that conform to research-related formats and structures; and weak understanding of the epistemological and practical methodological limitations of methods of literature analysis, data analysis and data collection, i.e. the philosophical basis of knowledge development. Experience indicates that conventional methods are ineffective in addressing these PhD level writing and reasoning shortfalls via short lectures, seminars, or courses. Observation of doctoral candidates' learning relating to these issues suggested that for most candidates the material provided by such programs is usually the wrong material presented at the wrong time (i.e. not well target to individual PhD candidates), and is both not enough and too much, and irrelevant to the stage of research the candidate is undertaking). One component of addressing some of these thesis writing issues is via Perry's 5 Chapter Thesis structure (Perry, 1994, 1998), later extended by Love as a result of exploring its use in PhD education in Design and related subject areas (Love, 2001, 2005a, 2005b). In parallel, supervisors are in a wonderful position to address the above issues efficiently and with precision because the problems and the necessary responses are specific to individual PhD candidates and each supervisor is in close connection with their PhD candidates.

In outline, the general format of the 'Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD supervision' method comprises: weekly meetings between supervisor and PhD student in which the student presents material that they

have written since the previous meeting and which contributes directly to their current stage of PhD; detailed advice on helping the candidate address the learning weaknesses revealed each week; ongoing individual training of the PhD candidate in the personal and professional skill so being a doctor; the use of a highly structured PhD thesis format; limiting the PhD thesis to 80,000 words; the choice of a research topic appropriate to a 3 year high quality PhD that is worth at least \$500,000 to society, there are many interesting topics but only a small proportion are appropriate to PhD research training; tightly managed time commitments; literature research by the supervisor for them to be ahead of the candidate in the knowledge related to the candidate's PhD; effective management of the PhD administration to ensure the PhD is not delayed by problems cause by university administration processes, including acting effectively on behalf of the candidate to remove delays; personal and front-line pastoral care support for the candidate; and proofreading of all document submissions by the candidate, providing suggestions for revisions and for the candidate's professional learning and skill development.

This is an outline. There are many detailed aspects of the 'quality 3-year fast-track supervision' method that have been omitted from this paper for brevity (methods of choosing a research project, points to address at each supervision meeting, style of document editing suggestions, underlying pedagogical processes and philosophy, addressing student skill problems, mentoring research methods development, choosing examiners, identifying the correct standard for sections of the PhD thesis, etc).

The quality 3-year Fast-Track supervision method appears effective and able to provide the results expected, particularly for candidates whose undergraduate education has been in Design-related subjects, and international students undertaking a long-thesis PhD in a university in which English is the requisite language for theses.

The application of this 'Quality 3-year Fast-Track Supervision' method appears to gain the benefits for the PhD candidate and other stakeholders of more efficient and effective PhD supervision. Its careful time management approach reveals, however, tension between the times needed for both best practice and conventional PhD supervision and the time allowances allocated by universities. This latter issue is addressed by the author in detail in a separate publication that focuses specifically on the tasks and time commitments for PhD supervision.

Conclusion

This paper has outlined the 'Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD Supervision' method developed by the author based on empirical research into PhD outcomes, PhD study and PhD supervision over the last decade. The paper provides reasons why developing an improved approach to PhD supervision of long thesis PhDs is essential. The paper describes some of the changing of factors acting on PhD education, particularly that of the long-thesis PhD. These new changes in the factors shaping PhD education are the results of and consequences of dissatisfaction by various stakeholders with current long-thesis PhD outcomes. Taken together, this new and developing PhD education context presents the design problem in response to which the 'Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD supervision' method outlined in this paper was designed and developed to address.

The paper outlines why and how each aspect of this new PhD supervisory method contributes to addressing and resolving the concerns widely-held about PhD outcomes, and at the same time ensures the candidate undertakes sound PhD-level research, writes a high quality PhD thesis, and gains the professional and personal skills and competencies expected of a professional PhD level research and completes within 3 years. Moreover, this supervision approach also addresses these same issues and concerns in the context of international PhD students disadvantaged by language and culture, and PhD candidates, such as those from Design-related fields, whose undergraduate education presents problems via lack of research training and over emphasis on rhetoric at the expense of reasoning and avoidance of fallacies. These latter, particularly, international PhD candidates are a significant concern to universities as they present potentially beneficial opportunities for financial expansion

In summary, the paper describes a PhD supervisory approach that provides universities and schools with a comprehensive basis to significantly improve PhD outcomes (time to completion and retention), in particular with those student cohorts that potentially provide significant financial benefits for universities but are currently presenting concerns to stakeholders due to low rate of completions and delays in completions.

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